

COGNIT: Challenges and Vision for a Serverless and Multi-Provider Cognitive Cloud-Edge Continuum

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Abstract—Use of the serverless paradigm in cloud application development is growing rapidly, primarily driven by its promise to free developers from the responsibility of provisioning, operating, and scaling the underlying infrastructure. However, modern cloud-edge infrastructures are characterized by large numbers of disparate providers, constrained resource devices, platform heterogeneity, infrastructural dynamicity, and the need to orchestrate geographically distributed nodes and devices over public networks. This presents significant management complexity that must be addressed if serverless technologies are to be used in production systems. This *position paper* introduces COGNIT, a major new European initiative aiming to integrate AI technology into cloud-edge management systems to create a *Cognitive Cloud* reference framework and associated tools for serverless computing at the edge. COGNIT aims to: 1) support an innovative new serverless paradigm for edge application management and enhanced digital sovereignty for users and developers; 2) enable on-demand deployment of large-scale, highly distributed and self-adaptive serverless environments using existing cloud resources; 3) optimize data placement according to changes in energy efficiency heuristics and application demands and behavior; 4) enable secure and trusted execution of serverless runtimes. We identify and discuss seven research challenges related to the integration of serverless technologies with multi-provider Edge infrastructures and present our vision for how these challenges can be solved. We introduce a high-level view of our reference architecture for serverless cloud-edge continuum systems, and detail four motivating real-world use cases that will be used for validation, drawing from domains within Smart Cities, Agriculture and Environment, Energy, and Cybersecurity.

Keywords— *serverless, FaaS, edge computing, resource management, multi-provider, cognitive cloud, open source*

I. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing infrastructures are rapidly evolving from centralized large-scale facilities into complex, heterogeneous, and distributed federations of devices and heterogeneous datacenters – often located at the edge of the network. These *cloud-edge continuum* systems have several characteristics that differentiate them from traditional Clouds; these include:

- *Multiple disparate providers.* Continuum systems consist of multiple infrastructure providers, which may operate multiple administrative domains [1]. This must be taken into account when designing continuum-based systems [2].
- *Platform heterogeneity.* In part as a result of having multiple disparate providers, platform heterogeneity must be assumed in a cloud-edge continuum. Nodes consist of different types of hardware, security solutions, etc. This creates significant integration issues; existing solutions are dominated by proprietary silos and incompatible technologies built around dedicated devices and run-time stacks [3].
- *Constrained resource devices.* As the number of Internet of Things (IoT) devices rapidly grows, cloud-edge continuum systems increasingly need to facilitate the processing requirements of devices with constrained resources [4]. This results in a need to provide code offloading capability, often whilst minimizing latency and energy consumption.
- *Infrastructural dynamicity.* Continuum infrastructures exhibit pronounced dynamicity, due to on-off switching of

IoT devices, mobility of edge nodes, and unreliable access links [5]. Applications and management systems within a continuum environment therefore need to be adaptive to frequently changing infrastructure.

- *The need to securely orchestrate geographically distributed nodes and devices over public networks.* Large multi-provider continuum infrastructures may include both private and public networking; however, in the general case, public networking must be assumed. This raises security and privacy concerns which must be taken into account when orchestrating data and applications across the infrastructure.

These characteristics greatly increase the *complexity of managing cloud-edge continuum infrastructures and the devices and applications that use them.* This poses a substantial integration challenge (technical and business) for providers, and a significant barrier to entry for developers and end users.

Serverless computing [6] is an emerging paradigm that offers the potential to significantly reduce this complexity (particularly on the user side) – and thus facilitate the uptake of cloud-edge continuum infrastructures. Serverless technologies aim to abstract infrastructure concerns away from applications; developers implement application functionality as invocable services (this model is typically referred to as *Function-as-a-Service - FaaS*), whilst providers automatically provision, deploy, and scale these services based on a range of criteria including efficiency, cost, load balancing, etc.

While this server-agnostic model to some extent mitigates several of the characteristics mentioned previously (e.g. it offers simplified code-offloading possibilities for constrained devices, removes the need for application developers to be concerned with infrastructural dynamicity etc.), several clear research challenges must be addressed to create a working multi-provider serverless infrastructure for cloud-edge continuums. Cross-cutting these challenges is the need for systems to adapt to changing user and provider requirements, system and network behaviors, and wider factors such as energy sustainability. At scale, this adaptability necessitates AI monitoring and control at all levels of the stack – creating a *Cognitive* cloud-edge system.

Section 2 of this position paper discusses seven key research challenges that must be addressed to bring the serverless vision to multi-provider cloud-edge continuums alongside proposed solutions. Section 3 presents our initial work on an open reference architecture for serverless cloud-edge continuums which we aim to validate using concrete use cases presented in Section 4. We conclude our vision and proposals in Section 5.

II. RESEARCH CHALLENGES AND POTENTIAL SOLUTIONS

Although serverless is seen as a good solution to several of the management challenges discussed in Section 1, key challenges must be addressed to bring this vision to reality. We identify seven research challenges that must be solved prior to creating an open serverless cloud-edge continuum architecture.

A. Cognitive cloud-edge management

The management of virtualized environments in the cloud is challenging mainly because of its scale, elasticity, and variability [7]. The cloud-edge continuum adds additional complexity due to its decentralized nature, large number of disparate providers, and need to orchestrate enormous numbers of geographically distributed nodes and devices over public networks. As discussed in Section 1, this imposes challenges in the management of compute, storage, and network [8]. For example, application data in geo-distributed storage systems requires data locality, support for user mobility, and fault tolerance - as well as entailing privacy and security concerns [9]. Additionally, applications may require the orchestration and coordination of network services like Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) or SDN-like capabilities across the cloud-edge networks [10].

From a technology perspective, the main open source cloud management platforms provide extensions (OpenNebula’s ONEedge, OpenStack’s StarlingX, CNCF’s KubeEdge, etc.) for extending virtualized and containerized application orchestration capabilities to hosts at edge. However, they have been developed mainly for homogeneous datacenters and lack the cognitive adaptability and automation features needed to operate on environments with constrained, heterogeneous, and dynamic resources. Conversely, major cloud providers are now beginning to offer pre-configured appliances (e.g. AWS Outpost, Azure Stack, etc.) that promise to bring the power of the public cloud to the private and edge cloud, and to define collaborations with telcos (e.g. Google and ATT, AWS and Vodafone) to create new 5G edge services. However, these are proprietary approaches that lock in users to particular technology stacks and limit innovation in the domain.

The Cognitive cloud-edge continuum requires a new generation of management platforms on highly distributed infrastructures that combine automated provisioning and scalability with an aggregated view of workloads and resources to enable AI-driven scheduling and optimization, and the development of energy efficiency and global security policies. We propose to extend the disaggregated cloud management model [11], which has been previously demonstrated by OpenNebula [12] for virtualized environments and partially incorporated into ONEedge, to manage the execution of serverless Runtimes on highly distributed data processing environments. The model will incorporate a full DevOps approach for infrastructure management. The use of programmatic tools is a requirement to address the scale of the cloud-edge continuum and for the on-demand deployment of the edge Points of Presence (PoPs) on on-premises and bare-metal infrastructure provider resources

B. Seamless user access and programming models

The emerging mobile cloud has expanded the horizon of application development and deployment with techniques such as code offloading to augment the computational capabilities available for applications with elastic cloud resources. Fast computational units and services (e.g. GPUs) and low-latency

connections (i.e. 5G) allow for computationally intensive data processing models to be executed outside the edge devices, sensors, and actuators. The advantages of using code offloading translate to more efficient power management [13], fewer storage requirements, and better application performance where devices may not provide the hardware acceleration capabilities for increasing the performance of the critical regions of computations. Different scenarios and use cases [14], whereby computation is fully or partially offloaded to Mobile Edge locations, have been presented to address a wide range of domains such as gaming, connected vehicles, and several services to provide high-quality communication services.

Although code offloading has been widely considered [15] to save energy and increase responsiveness of mobile devices, the technique still faces many challenges pertaining to practical usage [16], namely the complexity of its integration with the cloud management environment, the dynamic configuration of the system, its scalability, and the lack of Offloading-as-a-Service implementations. There are recent research efforts to expand the applicability of FaaS-based computation offloading to edge environments. For instance, Deviceless Edge Computing [17] is a new paradigm that aims to enable IoT and Edge devices, such as gateways and micro clouds, to be seamlessly integrated as application execution infrastructure. Although they show promising perspectives, most of these attempts are at early stages.

We propose to address existing code offloading limitations by developing a new distributed serverless model that, when integrated with a Cognitive management platform, facilitates the development of elastic and scalable edge-based applications. The framework will enable developers to offload tasks with dynamic execution requirements in terms of special hardware devices (e.g. GPU), infrastructure capabilities and capacities, specific execution environments, communication patterns, cost performance, latency, security, and energy efficiency.

C. New Serverless functionalities

Serverless computing has been rapidly adopted by developers because it relieves them of the burden of provisioning, scaling, and operating the underlying infrastructure. Since its appearance in AWS Lambda in 2014, the serverless computing paradigm has been rapidly emerging in the IT industry with major public cloud providers (e.g. Azure Functions, Google Cloud Functions) introducing comparable FaaS offerings and several open-source initiatives (Apache OpenWhisk, Iron Functions, Fission, Kubeless, OpenFaaS).

Existing serverless cloud solutions have many challenges [30]; these include assuming that cloud platforms run on large, highly homogeneous datacenters with commodity infrastructure, and that functions have a small footprint and short execution duration. Some research projects are addressing the challenges of using FaaS cloud models across multiple provider locations e.g. PHYSICS (<https://physics-faas.eu>), and the efficient distribution of big-data workloads along the compute continuum e.g. CLASS (<https://class-project.eu>). However, the

application of the FaaS model to distributed edge environments brings many challenges [18] such as cold starts, continuous workloads, edge AI, location-awareness, energy-awareness, resource specification, distributed networking, reliability, and security, derived from the dynamicity and heterogeneity at the edge, and the topology of network connectivity. Moreover, edge applications may require long-term execution using special-purpose hardware devices (e.g. GPUs, FPGAs) and pre-defined execution environments with AI libraries and services.

The new serverless cloud-edge computing model proposed in the COGNIT project is not only an infrastructural evolution of existing cloud serverless environments in which the computing resources that deliver serverless functions are highly distributed and may be located geographically closer to the end user (i.e. at the Internet's edge). While many of the technologies and best practices that have been developed for cloud serverless computing will form the basis of those for the cloud-edge, the model will provide new functionalities to manage the dynamicity and heterogeneity at the cloud-edge, the need to distribute computing and storage capabilities across a variety of providers, and the integration of special-purpose cloud and edge locations and services needed by the use cases.

D. Deployment and migration of serverless functions

Compared to a traditional serverless solution of hiring resources from a single cloud provider, the Cognitive cloud-edge model combines infrastructure resources from different on-premises deployments, and cloud and edge providers. In these environments, serverless is not only a technology that hides unnecessary infrastructure management details on each provider but also a platform that seamlessly and securely extends these benefits to the multi-provider cloud-edge continuum.

The current cloud-edge landscape is characterized by an ever-growing ecosystem of application formats, APIs and service portfolios. *Cloud portability* enables the migration of services between cloud providers or between a public cloud and a private cloud in response to a price increase, a breached service-level agreement, changing application requirements, or to fulfill a business need, such as moving cloud-based resources to another provider or edge location that is geographically closer to the consumers of the cloud service. While there are some standardization efforts to achieve interoperability among cloud providers, like the IEEE P2301 Guide for Cloud Portability and Interoperability [19], its adoption by Industry is very low.

There is a need to create innovative techniques to define software-defined overlays that abstract the differences between cloud and edge environments and significantly simplify the challenges of using multiple cloud providers. Portability of workloads across providers has traditionally been achieved by creating an application or Platform as a Service (PaaS) overlay, e.g. using container platforms as a standard way to deploy edge applications [20], that decouples the edge infrastructure from the workload. Some vendors are adding multi-cloud management features based on offering container platforms (e.g. Kubernetes) deployed across a multi-cloud environment (e.g. Google

Anthos, Microsoft Azure Arc, etc.). These solutions are far from achieving true portability across multi-cloud providers as they rely on specific container platform features and do not offer workload migration and self-adaptation.

COGNIT will develop new techniques and mechanisms for creating a software overlay that enables the deployment and migration of serverless functions across edge Points of Presence, and their self-adaptive execution with vertical scale up/down to adapt capacity to data processing needs. The edge architecture of the serverless system will be based on lightweight microVM virtualization technologies (e.g. Firecracker) and lightweight container orchestration technologies (e.g. K3s) that combine the resource efficiency of containers with the enhanced security and workload isolation of hypervisors.

E. AI modules and optimisation techniques

Existing resource management mechanisms are separated for datacenter, fog, and edge, making it cumbersome for applications that need computation in different layers. Autonomous resource management is vital to ensuring the efficiency, performance, and stability of cloud-edge continuum systems. However, this is predicated on rapid, accurate, and continually updated forecasts of system behavior (performance and energy implications of orchestrating workloads in different locations, on different hardware, etc.). The creation of such forecasts in continuum systems is a profound research challenge—new methods need to be developed to allow behavioral models to be constructed, monitored, and retrained in a lightweight, accurate, and timely manner. Furthermore, management systems that utilize these models need to be developed to balance both local and global optima to maintain even power distribution across regions, maximize climate efficiency (e.g. utilizing nodes that have energy available from renewable sources), guarantee service-level agreements, etc.

Existing autonomous resource management systems in cloud-edge continuum environments typically optimize on single objectives; the most recent approaches [21][22] attempt to address this, but still fail to consider the sheer number of interactions and objectives that cloud-edge continuum systems may possess (e.g. orchestrating to maximize use of renewable energy sources, optimizing placement based on hardware heterogeneity, heat generation, etc.). Further, the existing methods have sub-optimal task placement and elasticity that maximize cost and overall performance across the continuum.

We propose to develop scalable, multi-variate AI-enabled modeling and optimization techniques that function in large-scale, serverless, continuum environments, alongside the autonomous management mechanisms necessary to utilize these models. COGNIT will also explore and develop new methods to rapidly create and retrain ML-based predictive behavioral forecasts for all major management considerations faced by cloud-edge continuum environments, whilst minimizing model creation/retraining latency and impact on the system. Further, the model will consider the quality of data (QoD), Quality of Information (QoI), and Quality of Service (QoS) through a novel

engineering approach for obtaining cost-effective data for learning models that work across the cloud-edge continuum.

Ultimately, we will develop a holistic approach for blending intelligence into a Cognitive cloud-edge continuum architecture: 1) Continual learning-driven optimal on-demand resource allocation for the continuum; the primary goal of this method is to learn without accessing historical data from each layer of the continuum for dynamic allocation of resources for tasks that need to decide where and when they need computation. 2) Seq2Seq learning models to predict energy consumption and workloads in the continuum; we will explore multivariate and multi-objective optimization mechanisms that learn from historical data to offer cost-effective prediction of energy and workload for reducing cost and maximizing system performance. 3) Contrastive learning for developing cost-effective, secure, and performance models; monitoring data across a continuum typically shifts distribution over time, impacting model performance (i.e., learning, disaggregated inference); we aim to develop novel contrastive learning and optimization mechanisms that ensure cost-effective task placement, orchestration, energy-efficient, and elasticity across the cloud-edge continuum.

F. Energy efficiency and adaptation to green energy

Existing energy optimization frameworks for resource management in cloud-edge computing typically consider static, pre-defined models of energy usage, energy availability, workloads, etc., in fairly homogeneous, static environments. The energy usage in these models (often minimized in terms of total energy cost) rarely reflects sustainability aspects or the dynamic and heterogeneous nature of modern energy systems and power grid constraints. Reinforcement learning, having proved successful in optimizing datacenter cooling, has recently been explored as a way to take advantage of available data and adapt to such dynamic environments [23]. As an example, to improve sustainability of their datacenters, Google has recently integrated day-ahead forecasts of carbon intensity of the local energy supply to schedule and migrate tasks with long (up to 24-hour) deadlines [24].

However, existing approaches still lack a holistic approach to long-term energy and sustainability optimization, based on data-driven energy profiling and energy forecasts, capable of dealing with the heterogeneity and real-time fluctuations of local energy systems in highly distributed cloud-edge continuums. It is also necessary to develop new metrics and KPIs to measure energy performance in such environments—a task which is complicated by lack of available performance data and discrepancies in the evaluation procedures [25].

The Cognitive cloud-edge management layer developed by COGNIT will offer an aggregated view of workloads and resources to enable the development of energy efficiency and global security policies. Since nodes in the cloud-edge continuum will have heterogeneous local energy systems (configuration of renewables, energy storage, local grid, etc.), intelligent power management is needed, capable of responding

on the fly to changes in local grid conditions and variability in renewable energy supply. COGNIT will develop, as part of the disaggregated cloud management layer, new: 1) Heuristics and metrics for evaluating energy and sustainability performance in heterogeneous cloud-edge environments; 2) Data-driven ML methods for profiling compute nodes and workloads, based on these performance metrics, and predicting them; 3) A grid-aware hierarchical multi-constraint (temporal, latency, etc.) resource management layer to allocate workloads (both in time and geolocation), based on these profiles and multi-temporal forecasts of power and renewable supply, to maximize these performance metrics where global security policies should be orchestrated across the cloud-edge continuum; and 4) A holistic study and standardized approach to energy performance evaluation that takes into account the whole energy life cycle in the context of cloud-edge environments, and other sustainability aspects such as leveled cost of energy considering different energy carriers, validated using real use cases.

G. Secure and trusted execution of computing environments

Unlike serverless cloud platforms which operate in secured environments, the COGNIT framework runs on multi-provider resources and is exposed to threats and attacks on container computing, communications, and storage, requiring much better protection and isolation for the Serverless Runtimes. Current serverless platforms rely on Role Based Access Control (RBAC) mechanisms for authorization. While RBAC is simple to understand and use, more advanced access control schemes (e.g. based on policies or attributes) provide a finer control. Various solutions exist for microservices architectures [26] that can be adapted for serverless architectures in the Cloud/Edge to protect their heterogeneous and changing attack surface, and a trend of new tools based on eBPF are emerging[31].

To protect edge devices or workloads running on untrusted cloud infrastructures against attackers trying to read the data “in use”, trusted (or confidential) computing methods can be used where the data is protected by “Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)” such as Intel Software Guard Extensions (SGX) or AMD Secure Encrypted Virtualization (SEV). Frameworks have been proposed to leverage trusted computing in the context of FaaS such as the S-FaaS solution based on OpenWhisk and SGX. Such enclaves still suffer from vulnerabilities [27] that are difficult to detect. Anomaly detection solutions such as Rancher OPNI can help with the vulnerability assessment of serverless applications deployed on Kubernetes clusters and of the clusters themselves. This solution could provide anomaly detection in TEEs and in the edge by integrating with frameworks such as KubeEdge to ensure a low latency and resilient response at the edge. The ability to scale or migrate anomaly detection processing and data could help deal with anomaly detection peaks, troughs and resource limitations.

Finally, anomaly detection relies on various machine learning techniques using more or less supervised approaches [28][29]. To avoid sharing sensitive data between edges during training while ensuring autonomous anomaly detection can be done in each edge, the OPNI solution can be extended to

integrate with federated learning frameworks such as Flower or TensorFlow Federated. With federated learning, confidential or private data can be processed under the control of the data owner or controller, with only learned models shared. This allows processing to respect privacy legislation e.g. GDPR by design.

COGNIT proposes to develop new methods for: 1) Orchestration of global cloud-edge security policies, and integration of security constraints into cloud-edge application deployment; 2) Orchestration-level constraints by identifying application level components and data that need to be processed in an enclave based on organizational, infrastructure, and application level security and privacy policies; 3) Orchestration-level reasoning to determine where in the cloud-edge continuum processing can be done securely; 4) Deployment reasoning based on trusted/confidential computing constraints in cloud-edge deployments; 5) Use of confidential and trusted computing to secure computation of highly confidential or private data at the edge or in the cloud; and 6) Federated learning for low latency and privacy-respecting anomaly detection of serverless and FaaS services in Cloud/Edge.

III. COGNITIVE SERVERLESS CLOUD-EDGE ARCHITECTURE

Meeting these research challenges is a difficult task and requires coordination at many different layers of the cloud-edge stack. Our main assumptions for managing the cloud-edge continuum are that: (1) abstraction is key because users don’t control a continuum infrastructure that is usually offered by multiple providers; (2) rigid sandboxing is needed because the resources integrated in the continuum are untrusted environments; (3) an extremely scalable and elastic model for compute is needed because real-time processing demands at scale are unpredictable; and (4) the processing must be executed outside the devices to reduce costs through lower hardware complexity as well as compute resource sharing amongst a complete device fleet. The architecture of the proposed framework (shown in Fig. 1) consists of five major components:

- *Device client* is an SDK that creates *Serverless Runtime* environments for off-loading function executions on the continuum and performing tasks such as function execution, transfer of data from external sources, and transferring data from the device to the runtime to improve data locality.
- *Serverless Runtime* is the main unit management component of the COGNIT framework. It consists of two main components: a FaaS runtime that allows the execution of functions, and a DaaS (Data as a Service) runtime that will upload and transfer data in a hardened and secure environment along the cloud-edge continuum.
- *Provisioning Engine* is a stateless component responsible for managing the life cycle of the Serverless Runtimes; it can create, delete and update the Runtimes according to operations sent by the Device. It communicates with the Cognitive Cloud-Edge Module for the allocation and scheduling of the Serverless Runtimes across the cloud-edge continuum resources.

Figure 1. High-level cognitive serverless Cloud-Edge architecture

The final two architectural components are grouped together as part of the Cognitive Cloud-Edge Module that allows the management of the cloud-edge continuum resources in an intelligent and adaptive way.

- *Cloud-Edge Manager* is responsible for managing the highly distributed and heterogeneous resources of the cloud-edge continuum to schedule Serverless Runtimes according to the device/applications requirements.
- *AI-Enabled Orchestrator* produces an initial deployment plan according to the device requirements. It will update the deployment plan in case of updated requirements sent by the device, but it will also dynamically optimise the Serverless Runtime placement, taking into account the monitoring of resources (e.g. microVM, VMs etc.) used by the Runtime and the application metrics it reports.

To respond to the demands of European businesses and governments, the design of our cloud-edge platform will furthermore incorporate the following *transversal priorities*:

- *Security by Design*. Security needs to be considered as a transversal requirement that ensures the integrity of the data allocated, processed, and consumed at edge locations.
- *Sovereignty by Design*. COGNIT will analyze the requirements and practical implications of a sovereign approach when it comes to processing of data across cloud/edge infrastructures and applications.

- *Sustainability by Design*. COGNIT will take into account requirements to develop a sustainable smart edge platform that makes application developers and providers aware of the energy impact of their environments.
- *Interoperability by Design*. COGNIT will combine infrastructure resources from corporate datacenters and cloud-edge providers to provide a uniform environment for containers, unikernels, serverless, and Kubernetes.

We propose a management and orchestration model for the cognitive cloud-edge continuum based on the following five innovative concepts:

A. Cloud-Edge Management Model

The orchestration of a highly distributed cloud-edge infrastructure, consisting of multiple cloud and edge nodes spanning multiple providers and locations, represents a great challenge. The following requirements should be met:

- *Centralized view of the overall infrastructure*. The infrastructure should provide operators with a sensible set of operational metrics and a uniform view of its state. However, this centralized management should be compatible with the management of such a large infrastructure by incorporating additional capabilities like federation or streamlined management.
- *Management of sovereignty of multiple providers and on-premises resources*. Typical cloud-edge systems not only comprise of multiple locations but also multiple providers, each with its own APIs, offers, price models and features. The management layer needs to integrate these under a uniform layer that also includes on-premises resources.
- *Advanced application and resources monitoring to enable AI-driven optimization*. Such a complex and dynamic system requires an allocation mechanism able to optimize the resulting cloud-edge infrastructure to different metrics, such as the infrastructure cost or software power consumption. To support such logic, a reliable monitoring subsystem must be considered as part of the present model. The metrics gathered will also be used by the AI module for Workload Orchestration (described below) to improve the reliability of the infrastructure by anticipating failure conditions. Finally, we also plan to inject application-specific metrics in the monitoring system so not only the edge infrastructure will be considered by the optimization module but also the virtualized infrastructure running on it.

The cloud-edge management platform will be based on OpenNebula and the Edge Computing extensions developed in the ONEedge project, which will be enhanced with major innovations driven by the needs of the Project and its research-driven edge use cases.

B. Distributed Serverless Model for Edge App Development

To provide users with seamless access to a continuous data processing environment, developers need to easily integrate cloud-edge processing in their coding logic using a distributed

Table 1. Comparison between existing cloud technologies and the COGNIT serverless model

Characteristic	Existing FaaS Cloud Model	Cognitive Serverless Cloud-Edge Model
Programming		
Programming model	Interconnected functions (code) defined at a Cloud provider	Single program source code on device that follows an asynchronous model
Where the function runs	On Cloud provider	On Edge location
When the function is run	On event, cloud event-driven	On demand, application logic-driven
Application profile	Low footprint	Compute-intensive data processing
Program state	Stateless	Stateless / Stateful
Maximum runtime	Short (e.g. <900 seconds)	None
Maximum capacity	Limited (e.g. < 3GiB memory)	None
Communication patterns	Workflows and state machines	Results forwarding to other functions
Deployment requirements	Basic capacity (e.g. memory) & quotas	Performance, cost, security, and energy
Operation		
Scaling	Cloud provider responsible	Cloud provider responsible
Deployment	Cloud provider responsible	Cloud provider responsible
Fault Tolerance	Cloud provider responsible	Cloud provider responsible
Infrastructure		
Infrastructure	Single centralized cloud	Dynamic distributed cloud-edge
Location	Single centralized cloud	Developer selects (Internet's edge)
Special-purpose devices	None	Hardware (GPU), services (AI)

computing model to allow them to offload data processing code fragments and tasks from the end-user system, device, sensor, or actuator to a cognitive continuum to speed up computation, save energy, save bandwidth, or provide low latency.

Table 1 summarizes the main differences between the proposed distributed serverless model and the serverless/FaaS model implemented by existing cloud offerings and technologies. Developers will use a Domain-Specific Library (DSL) for developing edge applications and defining the execution of the server logic (functions) in distributed Serverless Runtimes (container-like environments) that may be located geographically closer to the end user of the application. Developers have control over network, computing and data services, and infrastructure assigned to their execution by defining attributes in terms of:

- Execution Context attributes such as life-time, compute/network/storage needs, data processing variability, and specific processing infrastructure (e.g. Cloud, HPC), hardware (e.g. GPUs), or services (e.g. database, AI).
- Base Image with application-specific operating system, libraries, and packages such as databases.
- Communication Patterns for example to define parallelism and distribution in execution of FaaS Runtimes.
- Deployment Requirements for performance, cost, security, location and energy

The Device client establishes a communication with the Provisioning Engine to request:

- Offloading of certain operations, tasks, or algorithms to be executed on Serverless Runtime(s) on the continuum.
- Relocation and mobility of Serverless Runtime(s) considering dynamic changes in requirements.

The Provisioning Engine is responsible for managing the life-cycle of the Serverless Runtimes and it interacts with the cloud-edge Manager to submit the requests for scheduling the creation of Serverless Runtimes according to the Device requirements, and negotiates its relocation considering dynamic changes of Serverless Runtime requirements or changes in the requirements sent by the Device.

C. Distributed Computing in Multi-Provider Cloud-Edge

Given the heterogeneity of cloud-edge systems, we propose a model structured over the concept of a serverless “Edge Cluster” to create an abstraction layer across the multi-provider cloud-edge. An edge cluster is a semi-autonomous resource set (storage, network, and compute), able to work on unreliable infrastructures and allocated in given edge locations with:

- *Automatic configuration and deployment with resource scaling out/in.* A programmatic and automatic approach to edge clusters is needed to manage (e.g. install, reconfigure, or patch) hundreds of locations. Moreover, a declarative definition is needed to express different edge cluster flavors suitable for different providers or location profiles. Finally,

being able to dynamically reconfigure or create edge clusters allows us to deploy an edge infrastructure that reshapes and reacts to different conditions (e.g. failures, performance usage, or energy consumption).

- *Environmental footprint optimization.* Dynamic adaptation of the processing capacity of the continuum to the varying supply of green energy and local grid conditions.
- *Edge node optimization.* The operation of a highly distributed set of edge locations requires specific solutions in terms of storage and networking that optimize behavior at the edge cluster level and adapt to the available resources. Note that even though some locations may support datacenter-grade components, their distributed nature demands specialized management techniques. Edge nodes can feature novel architectures (e.g. ARM-based) and integrated specialized devices (GPU) that should be exposed to the applications.
- *Up/down scaling self-regulation.* Dynamically change the capacity of the Serverless Runtime environment to adapt to application behavior and variability.
- *Self-healing.* In case of failure, the cluster can offer alternative resources capable of recovering from routine and extraordinary events that might cause some of its parts to malfunction.
- *Portability.* Thanks to the vendor-neutral abstraction layer built by the edge Clusters, the system should be able to easily migrate workloads across clusters.

FaaS Runtimes running at the edge are also diverse in nature and requirements, and a considerable number of applications are distributed as containers. However, container technologies (e.g. Docker, Kubernetes) come with serious limitations, such as security (application containers share the kernel OS) and multi-tenant environments. New alternative lightweight virtualization technology (e.g. Firecracker microVMs, K3s Lightweight Kubernetes) should be considered to create and manage microVMs that provide enhanced security and workload isolation over traditional VMs, while enabling the speed and resource efficiency of containers.

D. Automatic and Intelligent Adaptation

The monitoring metrics gathered by the Disaggregated Cloud Manager will be used by the AI-enabled application placement, Workload Orchestrator, and optimal resource management to:

- *Define where data is processed* according to Serverless Runtime deployment attributes for performance, cost, security, and energy requirements. While resources must be close to the final use for latency-sensitive applications, the resources must be close to the data sources for data-intensive applications. If edge resources are limited or insufficient, functions can be executed on the cloud for compute-intensive applications.

- *Implement dynamic load balancing* to respond to changing requirements from the application execution flow or to changes in capacity demanded by the Serverless Runtime due to data size or processing needs variability.
- *Optimize energy efficiency and reduce power grid congestion*, through optimized geographic distribution of workloads in distributed cloud-edge infrastructures that adapts in real-time, to available energy and reduces environmental impact - exploiting the opportunities offered by the edge-cloud continuum, while incentivizing the local generation and use of green energy.
- *Improve the reliability of the infrastructure* by anticipating failures and local power grid congestion.
- *Dynamic application task placement and orchestration* for cost-efficient, secure and optimal performance in the continuum layers through advanced deep learning methods.

E. Secure and Trusted Execution of Computing Environments on Multi-Provider Continuum

Unlike serverless cloud platforms which operate in secured environments, the COGNIT cloud-edge runs on multi-provider resources and it is exposed to various threats and attacks, requiring much better protection and isolation for the FaaS runtime containers. Our model includes:

- *Distributed anomaly detection* with observability and remediation mechanisms that can be deployed as close as possible to the FaaS Runtime and are lightweight enough to run on resource-constrained edge devices and avoid impacting the FaaS Runtime performance.
- *Federated learning techniques* that can be used to train models for AI-based security mechanisms (e.g. anomaly detection or automated security remediation) without exchanging the training data.
- *Confidential computing solutions*, for example software encryption of FaaS Runtime storage and hardware-based Trusted Execution Environments such as Intel SGX, that can be used to protect the FaaS Runtime and its data

IV. USE CASES

The definition of requirements and validation of our research will be done through the prototype implementation and pilot deployment of use cases making use of the AI-enabled platform in four application domains: Smart Cities, Agriculture and Environment, Energy, and Cybersecurity.

A. Use Case 1: Smart Cities

Distributed smart data processing capabilities, combined with connected vehicle technologies, can improve cities in terms of traffic congestion, pollution, and public safety. Transportation systems need to be interoperable, intelligent, secure and support the development of multi-tier edge applications that can be deployed across a cloud-edge continuum and managed securely using cloud native practices.

A major challenge in smart city use cases is the *management and optimization of diverse edge applications with different QoS requirements on resource-constrained edge/IoT devices*. Currently, these are managed using mostly proprietary client-server solutions deployed on city control center premises. There is a great benefit from cloud native solutions based on distributed microservices deployed close to the data sources, reducing overhead and distributing data processing workloads efficiently, allowing developers to maximize edge/IoT device capability while automating the offloading of specific heavy functions and processes to the cloud-edge continuum.

As part of COGNIT, a new solution for public transport priority management will be tested that combines next generation Traffic Light Controllers (TLC), with the Project's cognitive serverless framework to automate and carry out intelligent resource provisioning across the cloud-edge continuum based on edge applications' QoS requirements. This use case will involve the *Saturno* cloud platform (<https://www.acisa.es/en/innovation/saturno>), responsible for urban traffic management and analytics, and *Mobility-Hub* (<https://www.acisa.es/en/innovation>), an advanced TLC with edge capabilities, traffic sensors on the road and Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X) equipment in the vehicles.

Current public transport signalized intersection systems assign priority based on self-reported delay, regardless of other factors such as traffic congestion, weather conditions etc. The COGNIT Smart City use case will gather and process data from traffic detectors, the speed, location and direction of surrounding vehicles reported through C-V2X messages, bus schedule delays published by public transport management systems, weather conditions, etc. This information comes from different systems, through different channels and protocols, at different cadences, and must be processed in a matter of milliseconds to give the TLC enough time to safely adjust the timings of traffic lights.

Existing low-fidelity city models employed in traffic management mostly rely on centralized systems, with limited capacity to assess real-world scenarios with high accuracy and low latency. We will demonstrate and validate the concept of enhancing intersection modeling through the development of high-fidelity distributed Digital Twins. This will be achieved by performing computation as close to a vehicle requestor as possible, relying on the cloud continuum properties of COGNIT to abstract parts of the traffic management & public transport systems from the operations, nodes and communications used to achieve the result, i.e. processing is done in edge nodes installed in strategic locations in the city or relocated into network operators' infrastructure, such as that based on Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) or Akraio MicroMEC (μ MEC)[32], to leverage 5G edge resources for deploying services with low latency or high computation requirements, like distributed Digital Twins or C-V2X.

B. Use Case 2: Wildfire Detection

Europe has witnessed a significant increase in the number and ferocity of the so-called 'mega-fires', a phenomenon linked

with climate change. Edge/IoT devices, coupled with AI/ML, can play an important role in preventing and fighting wildfires. Information gathered from environmental sensors deployed in the forest not only offers better monitoring but also helps to predict, detect, and manage wildfires. By using a traditional cloud-centric model, latency and near-real-time analytics on the behavior and spread of wildfires cannot be achieved effectively due to the large amount of information transmitted. Improving the data processing capabilities of the edge applications that are closer to the response teams deployed on the ground, can provide a powerful tool for real-time assessment of wildfires.

Despite the rapid emergence of a new generation of devices and optimized coding libraries, processing capabilities of environmental sensors are still limited and their deployment in remote areas requires low energy consumption. Edge applications running in these devices will benefit from being able to access additional cloud-edge resources on demand through an FaaS engine.

COGNIT will prototype a distributed network for real-time wildfire detection combining Nature 4.0 sensors with the cognitive serverless framework. A new AI-powered edge application will be deployed on the devices, leveraging next-generation Arm Cortex M7 ultra-low-power microprocessors and micropython AI libraries, and making use of the cloud-edge continuum through an FaaS model to reduce latency time for processing real-time data and testing how to build a sustainable and secure service for local civil protection teams.

C. Use Case 3: Energy

Supporting energy transition in Europe requires allowing the wide and open accessibility of energy data. Due to diminishing energy resources (oil, gas, carbon) it is critical to develop solutions for individual energy independence of a household and/or small energy clusters.

This necessitates the development of methods for monitoring, predicting, and managing both energy production and consumption in a given environment. For this, the implementation of smart edge applications that make use of advanced AI/ML algorithms is needed.

Current deployments in the energy sector are limited by edge applications being deployed in resource-constrained environments (i.e. energy meters) and the very high security requirements for distribution system operators (DSO), which is usually a result of centralized architectures based on private DC infrastructures. Advanced AI/ML applications would benefit from being able to leverage, in a secure way, additional resources across the cloud-edge continuum that are much closer to the data sources and edge/IoT devices on the ground.

COGNIT will design and test a new edge application deployment model based on providing an energy production/consumption prediction service. This model will leverage the Project's cognitive serverless framework to allow AI/ML algorithms to offload workloads to the cloud-edge continuum by combining the application execution environment

in energy meters with the new FaaS engine. Data produced by the "Edge-IoT Meter" will monitor energy consumption, detect anomalies, and optimize energy usage.

D. Use Case 4: CyberSecurity

In the context of the intensification of cyber-attacks globally, the available attack surface of IT and OT systems keeps increasing. Moving computation and data processing services to the edge, far from secured datacenters, leaves systems exposed to new threats. Edge Computing requires a new generation of intelligent security mechanisms to be deployed along with edge applications, providing low latency and resilient anomaly detection and remediation, including privacy preserving mechanisms that use federated learning and implement advanced authentication and authorization policies. These solutions, especially those based on AI/ML algorithms, would benefit from being able to leverage additional resources on-demand across the cloud-edge continuum, and have to be tested and closely integrated with those container management technologies that dominate the market, especially with platforms based on Kubernetes (including SUSE's K3s lightweight distribution for far-edge environments).

COGNIT will design and test a use case focused on securing the development and operation of an FaaS workflow on a smart mobility solution at the edge. A DevSecOps pipeline will be implemented that integrates development, operations, and security activities to update and operate software deployed on simulated and physical autonomous rovers based on the Robot Operating System and the KubeEdge framework. This innovative DevSecOps approach will focus on providing distributed anomaly detection at the edge by extending the SUSE OPNI AIOps engine, applying confidential computing to protect data in the rovers not only at rest or in transit but also in use (during runtime), and will orchestrate the security response using the Vacsine SOAR (Security Orchestration, Automation, and Response) platform based on security policies. Anomaly detection must be distributed to collect data from the entire attack surface of the rover system that includes not only the rovers themselves operating in a platoon, but also the cloud/edge based traffic supervision system. Attacks could begin at any interface of the attack surface. The aim of distributed anomaly is to detect the anomalous behavior due to the intrusion as early as possible before the damage is done, e.g. by fault injection to cause rovers to crash.

V. CONCLUSION

This position paper introduces the key challenges and vision addressed by COGNIT – a major European initiative to develop an open architecture and platform to enable the development of a cognitive serverless cloud-edge continuum eco-system. The differences between multi-provider cloud-edge continuum systems and traditional cloud-edge infrastructures are introduced, and seven major research challenges are discussed. These research challenges are: 1) the need for disaggregated management systems; 2) enabling seamless user access across a continuum and developing appropriate programming models; 3)

new serverless functionalities including energy-awareness, distributed networking, etc.; 4) the need for innovative new techniques to develop software-defined overlays to abstract the differences between cloud and edge environments; 5) the need for cross-continuum monitoring, modelling, and optimization; 6) the need for advanced energy-aware scheduling across continuums; and 7) orchestration of global cloud-edge security policies and anomaly detection techniques.

Additionally, we present a new architecture that aims to address these challenges. This architecture will be developed throughout the COGNIT initiative and will ultimately be used by the European Union as a reference for future cloud-edge projects and software initiatives. In particular, we discuss the structure for a proposed distributed FaaS model for edge application development, a disaggregated cloud management model, a distributed model for serverless computing on cloud-edge continuum systems, automatic and intelligent adaption mechanisms based on monitoring data, and secure and trusted execution on multi-provider continuum systems.

Finally, we introduce real-world use cases that are both motivators for this initiative (and its associated research challenges) as well as validators that will be used to assess the effectiveness of the final system in production environments. These use cases are drawn from the domains of Smart Cities, Agriculture and Environment, Energy, and Cybersecurity.

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